

Pressure drop simulation for a compressed gas closed system

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Abstract

The objective of the project was to calculate by simulation, the pressure drop of a firefighting pressure regulated discharge valve for inert gas agent. For doing that, we simulate the discharge of a pressurized closed canister through the valve under realistic conditions.

This project has been done in collaboration with the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC). The code used to perform the numerical simulations is Alya, a multi-physics code developed at BSC. The code has been adapted to solve this application problem.

1. Introduction

FDD Engitec is a Spanish SME that designs and manufactures firefighting components and systems. Its core expertise is focused on the development of gaseous clean agent extinguishing systems. Its activities cover from the design of components and systems, validation tests, manufacturing and certification. It is oriented to the global market, but mainly based in the European and North Africa markets. The company main development expertise is mainly mechanical engineering: elasticity and material resistance and fluid mechanics for compressed and non-compressed fluids. FDD team is currently focused in the design of a new firefighting system that will use inert compressible fluid.

The objective was to calculate by simulation the pressure drop of a firefighting pressure regulated discharge valve for inert gas agent. For doing that, it is needed to simulate the discharge of a pressurized closed canister through the valve under realistic conditions. In fact, FDD Engitec is developing a valve that must completely exhaust the canister content within a certain time limit.

As the project was going on, it became apparent that the initial objective was too ambitious. The main reason was that to simulate the real configuration, which is a complex geometry with regions including very small elements and high speed compressible flows, we required much more resources than those provided by SHAPE. In the current development status of BSC's code Alya, we would require either a much larger amount of computational resources or a much larger programming and development effort. Therefore, we focused on simulating the first expansion stages instead of the whole process, analysing especially the temperature distribution and the regime's oscillatory behaviour.

2. Physical description

The problem was simulated using BSC's multi-physics code Alya [1]. The system's mechanics is governed by the viscous compressible flow Navier-Stokes equations. The equations are programmed following [2][3] where a thorough description of the methodology is given. Using a Finite Element Method-based space discretisation on

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unstructured meshes, time is discretized using Finite Differences and an explicit forward Euler scheme. Convective and low Mach instabilities are simultaneously controlled using a Variational Multiscale Stabilization (VMS) method. Although the inflow velocity could suggest a near incompressible flow, the system set up produces shock waves. This is mostly due both to the very high-pressure gradient at the inflow and the sudden narrowing in parts of the geometry. Then, shocks are stabilized with a shock capturing residual-weighted diffusion.

Flow dynamics is simulated under several assumptions. Firstly, we assume no phase changes. FDD engineers assure that although the initial pressure in the canister is very high, the fluid is in gaseous phase. Besides, during the strong expansion within the valve, we do not consider any phase change. Secondly, although the very high Reynolds numbers and as a preliminary assumption, we simulate laminar flow. The reason is that as we are not very confident on RANS models for such kind of flows, testing them would have required even further programming and development runs.

At the inlets, total pressure is imposed and the outlets are left free. The walls are considered adiabatic and no-slip condition is imposed on the velocity. We acknowledge that the boundary layer is only approximately resolved due to the large element sizes, but we left for further research to perform simulations on a better and larger mesh.

3. Simulations

3.1. Software

The Alya system is a multi-physics code developed in the Barcelona Supercomputing Center [4]. It is written in FORTRAN language and is based on a finite element formulation. It is parallelised using a hybrid MPI+OpenMP strategy. Alya is structured using a modular architecture organised in kernel, modules and services. The kernel contains all that is required to solve the different sets of discretised partial differential equations, while the modules provide the physical description of a given problem. In the present simulations, the module used for the fluid flow problem is NASTAL, for compressible flow. From its conception, the code is specifically designed to run efficiently in the assigned PRACE system. Nowadays, Alya belongs to the PRACE Benchmark Suite [5]. Regarding problem setup, commercial software, notably ICEM CFD and GiD were used to generate the meshes.

Alya has been improved to solve the flow problem of this SHAPE project. A new total pressure boundary condition has been implemented and tested. This condition is very useful for the kind of inflow/outflow we are facing here, where a big canister submitted to a certain pressure exerts a strong expansion upon a much lower pressure through a valve. The total pressure equation allows imposing the velocity computed from the flow rate. Additionally, and to perform the required simulations, we have further improved the total pressure boundary condition in a way that pressure progressively decays as the large tank loses material. This evolution function is based on mass conservation and some thermodynamic considerations. The idea is to replace simulating the canister itself with a certain boundary condition at the inlet of the valve geometry. Finally, a stabilization parameter analysis has been performed in order to correctly model the firefighting discharge valve.

3.2. Configuration

The real case conditions are the following:

- Initial pressure into the canister: 300 bar / 200 bar
- Final pressure into the canister: 0 bar
- In the canister there is just one outlet where the valve is installed.
- The valve itself can regulate the outlet discharge pressure to a fix value during the discharge by internal mechanical devices. Instead of changing the geometry, we suppose the "best case scenario" in which the valve is fully opened during the complete simulation.

We perform a set of simulations on two different configurations to study flow conditions within the valve. For that reason, instead of simulating the canister and the valve, we consider only the valve with a total pressure boundary condition to simulate the presence of the canister. A first set up is a simplified valve configuration, which reproduces the physical problem including dimensions and boundary conditions, is done to fine-tune running conditions especially on its numerical aspects. Once we establish the best running conditions, we perform a second round of simulations on a much larger scenario, with the original valve geometry. In both cases, we run the expansion with the valve fully open all the way.

In both cases, initial conditions were the following: zero velocity, normal dry air density and standard temperature and pressure (300K, 1 bar). Total pressure at the inflow is set to 300bar, which increases progressively following a steep ramp: it starts at 2 bar and reached linearly 300 bar in 0.03s.

3.2.1. Simplified configuration

Figure 1 and Figure 2 show a long axis cut of the simplified configuration. The inflow, coming from the canister, is at the bottom right and the outflow to the atmosphere is to the left. Both red and blue tubes are 2 cm diameter. Blue tube is 40 cm long and red tube is 18 cm long with an internal hollow part. Air expands from the inflow, runs around the hollow, enters into a small connecting tube 1 mm diameter and passes to the blue tube until it exits. Figure 3 shows a close-up of the connecting tube.

Figure 1. Simplified configuration. Long axis cut.

Figure 2. Simplified configuration. Colours represent the pressure at the first steps.

Figure 3. Simplified configuration. Connecting tube.

Although the mesh is very coarse, after the fine-tuning process the simulations run smoothly. Figure 4 shows the mesh around the connecting tube. Figure 5 shows a snapshot of the velocity field as it goes through the connection. Observe the strong acceleration as it moves from the vertical to the horizontal tubes.

Figure 6, Figure 7 and Figure 8 show a long axis cut for the velocity module distribution at different time steps.

Figure 9 shows the mean speed evolution at the inflow. Observe the oscillatory character due to the sound waves rebounding within the valve structure. At time 0.03s, total pressure at the inflow stabilizes and this discontinuity in pressure evolution produces another, yet smaller, train of oscillations.

After several runs of these tests for the simplified configuration, we established the optimal running scheme. It was an explicit formulation for the compressible flow Alya solver with VMS stabilization and isotropic shock capturing. Shock capturing was very useful to stabilize strong discontinuities in order to control Mach number peaks within the geometry, which could rise almost up to Mach 2, with strong temperature drops localized around the shocks.

Figure 4. Simplified configuration. Mesh close up. Long axis cut around the connecting tube.

Figure 5. Simplified configuration. Snapshot of the velocity field.

Figure 6. Simplified configuration. Snapshot of the velocity module.

Figure 7. Simplified configuration. Snapshot of the velocity module.

Figure 8. Simplified configuration. Snapshot of the velocity module.

Figure 9. Simplified configuration. Mean speed at the inflow.

3.2.2. Valve configuration

Once the fine-tuning runs were performed, we generate the mesh for the real valve configuration and start using the PRACE SHAPE supercomputing resources on MareNostrum III at BSC. The mesh for the real case was made of 7,048,193 tetrahedra. We performed several runs using 1024 cores in MareNostrum for several millions of time steps. Each run took between 12 and 24 hours.

The real geometry is very complex. Flow is forced to pass through a set of radial small holes to finally discharge on the long exhaust tube. As in the previous example, total pressure at the inflow is set to 300 bar, increasing progressively through a steep ramp: it starts at 2 bar and reaches linearly 300 bar in 0.03s. As was already observed in the simplified example, the high-pressure expansion produces Mach number peaks of around 2.

We also observed that for some extremely short periods of time (between 1/1000 and 1/100 sec) temperature drops well below zero, as far as -100 degrees. We remark that these temperature drops last for extremely brief times and are highly localized to reduced size volumes, probably not enough to be noted experimentally. However, there are larger regions with sustained low temperatures, as low as -30 degrees. If these low temperature regions remain enough time below zero, the valve's mechanical components can freeze, which could very likely end in a valve function failure.

Figure 10 shows the mean speed at the valve inflow, in blue sky. As in the simplified problem, we observe an oscillatory behaviour. In this case, oscillations take longer to get damped because the mesh is much finer resulting in a less dissipative scheme. However, the mean behaviour is very similar to the simplified configuration, including oscillations change at 0.03s, when the total pressure ramp achieves its maximum (300bar). In purple, we show the inflow mean speed for a much finer mesh, 56M tetrahedra. We construct this mesh by homogeneously subdividing the 7M tetrahedra mesh. Although we could not manage to run the refined mesh longer, we see that the behaviour is very similar.

Figure 10. Real valve configuration. Mean speed at the inflow. In blue, 7M element mesh and in purple, 56M mesh.

4. Conclusions

Due to the facts discussed above, we could not manage to simulate the full canister discharge process. Instead, we studied the first stages of the expansion to the valve. We have observed low temperature and high Mach regions within the valve that could lead to valve failures and fatigue. We have also observed a strong oscillatory flow behavior due to compressibility effects that could also lead to valve mal function. We have left open future collaborations with FDD Engitec. For such collaborations to take place, we need to secure a larger amount of resources, both computational and human, in order to study ways to improve firefighting equipment manufacturing through simulations.

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